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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

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Phylogenetic Analysis of Allotetraploid Species Using Polarized Genomic Sequences

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J. L. Leal, Pascal Milesi, Jarkko Salojärvi, and Martin Lascoux

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10 Read Mapping and Variant Calling: Detailed Description

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The pipeline used for library pre-processing, read mapping, and variant calling generally followed the GATK best practices workflow developed by the Broad Institute (DePristo et al. 2011, Poplin et al. 2018). Upon initial quality assessment of the Illumina libraries with FASTQC, v. 0.11.5 (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>), raw reads were split by sequencing-machine/run/flow-cell/lane and converted from fastq to uBAM format using the FastqToSam tool from the PICARD suite, v. 2.10.3 (<http://broadinstitute.github.io/picard/>). Read-group tags were also imputed during this step. Next, Illumina adapter sequences were identified and tagged using PICARD 's MarkIlluminaAdapters.

Reads were aligned to a single reference genome with BWA-MEM, v. 0.7.17 (Li and Durbin 2009), and PCR duplicates were picked out and marked with MarkDuplicates from the PICARD suite. All the *Arabidopsis* and *Capsella* accessions were mapped to the unmasked *A. lyrata* v2.1 reference genome (Hu et al. 2011, Rawat et al. 2015). On average, 85% of reads from off-target species were mapped (88% for *A. lyrata*; 53% for *Capsella*).

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Genotyping was performed with GATK, v. 3.8-0 (McKenna et al., 2010). Loci found to be non-variant after genotyping were also included in the output VCF file. Because samples were obtained from different *Brassicaceae* species, each library was processed separately. Site-level variant filtration was done with the VariantFiltration tool from the GATK suite according to the hard-filtering guidelines put forward by the Broad Institute (<https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/360035890471-Hard-filtering-germline-short-variants>, accessed 2021-04-30). SNPs and non-variant sites were filtered out (filter field in VCF file set to 'FAIL') if they matched at least one of the following criteria: “QD < 2.0”, “FS > 10.0”, “MQ < 40.0”, “SOR > 5.0”, “|MQRankSum| > 2.5”, “|ReadPosRankSum| > 2.5”, or “DP < (PL+1)”, where PL is the sample ploidy. The filter field for invariant sites with read depth (DP) > 0 was set to 'PASS'. Similar thresholds, aside from the MQ filter, which was omitted, were used when hard-filtering indels.

During genotyping, only sites found in scaffolds 1 to 8 and located in 23,868 single-copy orthogroups were considered (information about sites located outside these genomic regions was discarded). Single copy orthogroups were identified with ORTHOFINDER, v. 2.3.1 (Emms and Kelly 2015), using default options, based on the primary-transcript proteome. The final number of variants discovered, as well as the average read depth within the genes of interest, is shown in Table S2. Variant, non-variant, and missing sites were all included when computing the average read depth, which was performed using VCFTOOLS, v. 0.1.16 (Danecek et al. 2011).

We also ran a parallel pipeline where read mapping and variant calling were performed against the *A. halleri* v.2.2 reference genome (Briskine et al. 2017).

52 **Simulated datasets: Detailed Description**

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54 The main steps for the creation and analysis of simulated datasets are described below.

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56 (a) SIMPHY, v. 1.0.2 (Mallo et al. 2016), a phylogeny simulator that can be used to
57 simulate the evolution of gene families under the multispecies coalescent model, was used to
58 generate species trees and the associated individual gene trees evolving under ILS. We used
59 simulation conditions similar to those suggested by Mirarab and colleagues (Mirarab and
60 Warnow 2015; Zhang et al. 2018) to explore four different scenarios that reflect distinct levels
61 of ILS (moderate or very high) and speciation landscapes (recent or ancient speciation events).
62 For each scenario, we simulated 100 replicates (-rs 100), with each replicate based on a different
63 species tree. The species tree is randomly generated but included always 16 species (-sl f:16),
64 plus an outgroup, with two individuals per species (-si f:2). (The two individuals belonging to
65 the same species will be used to create diploid individuals in a subsequent step, and two species,
66 randomly selected, will be used to create the allotetraploid.) No extinction events were allowed
67 (-sd f:0). For each replicate, 1,200 independent gene families were generated (-rl f:1200).
68 Moderate levels of discordance between the species tree and individual gene trees were
69 simulated using the tree-wide parameters and substitution rate heterogeneity parameters listed
70 by Zhang et al. (Zhang et al. 2018) to create their *S100* dataset, while gene phylogenies with
71 high levels of ILS were simulated using the conditions used by the same authors to create the
72 more challenging *S200* dataset (Zhang et al. 2018; Mirarab and Warnow 2015). Following Zhang
73 et al. (Zhang et al. 2018), a speciation rate of 1×10^{-6} events/time unit (-sb f:0.000001) was used
74 to simulate phylogenies in which speciation events took place in the recent past. This value was
75 decreased to 1×10^{-7} when investigating deep speciation scenarios. Individual gene phylogenies
76 were checked after running SIMPHY in order to guarantee that, while levels of ILS across gene
77 families reflected simulation parameters, the two individuals belonging to the same species were

78 always grouped together. For exact list of commands used, see scripts (link provided at the end
79 of this paper).

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81 (b) Nucleotide sequence alignments, one for each gene tree simulated, were generated
82 with INDELIBLE, v. 1.03 (Fletcher and Yang 2009), using a modified version of the
83 INDELible_wrapper.pl script provided with the SIMPHY suite (SIMPHY manual,
84 <https://github.com/adamallo/SimPhy/wiki/Manual>, accessed 2021-08-05). For each replicate
85 created using SIMPHY, 80% of the 1,200 gene trees were used to generate an equal number of
86 MSAs by assuming gene families evolved under a HKY evolutionary model with the kappa
87 parameter, sampled de novo for each gene family, coming from an exponential distribution with
88 rate=1. The remaining MSAs (20%) were generated using a more complex evolutionary model
89 based on the GTR substitution model with rates sampled (once for each replicate) from a
90 Dirichlet (6,16,2,8,20,4) scaled with the last rate (INDELIBLE requirement), and rate
91 heterogeneities across sites modeled using a continuous gamma distribution with the alpha
92 parameter sampled from an exponential distribution with rate=2. In both cases, equilibrium
93 nucleobase frequencies were set to (0.25, 0.25, 0.25, 0.25). DNA sequence lengths were constant
94 within each MSA but varied across gene families. Gene lengths were sampled from a normal
95 distribution with a 1,500 bp mean value and a 150 bp standard deviation. Simulated MSAs
96 contained no indels.

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98 (c) Next, each of the 1,200 MSAs associated to each replicate was processed in order to
99 create diploid and tetraploid individuals. For each MSA, nucleotide sequences for the two
100 haploid individuals belonging to the same species were collapsed into a single sequence, creating
101 a diploid individual, with heterozygous sites coded using IUPAC nomenclature. Two species,
102 randomly selected, were used to create the allopolyploid individual; in this case, four haploid
103 sequences were collapsed into a single nucleotide sequence, with heterozygous sites again being

104 IUPAC recoded. The two parental species were subsequently removed from the MSA. As
105 haplotype information is lost when the two sequences associated to a particular species are
106 collapsed into a single sequence, the resulting MSA mimics those created using consensus
107 sequences produced from genotyping data inferred from real-world sequencing reads.

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109 (d) At this stage, simulated MSAs were processed using the same pipeline employed in
110 the analysis of the *Brassicaceae* MSAs. First, the allotetraploid is polarized using a reference
111 sequence selected randomly. This is followed by phylogenetic inference for each individual gene
112 family using IQ-TREE2. Finally, a species tree was inferred using ASTRAL on the basis of the
113 individual gene trees.

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180 Table S1 | **Sample information (*Arabidopsis* and *Capsella*)**. Specie's name, ploidy, number of
 181 chromosomes found in somatic cells, and sequencing technology used. Allopolyploid species
 182 highlighted in cyan. Autopolyploid species highlighted in pink. European Nucleotide Archive
 183 (ENA) accession numbers provided for whole genome sequencing (WGS) data publicly
 184 available (Novikova et al. 2016; Cao et al. 2011).

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Genus	Species	Sequencing	Ploidy	Polyploidization	Chromosome No.	Source ^a	ENA Run Accession
<i>Arabidopsis</i>	<i>A. arenosa ssp. arenosa</i>	WGS	diploid		$2n=2x=16$	PN	SRR2082782, SRR2082785
	<i>A. arenosa ssp. arenosa</i>	WGS	tetraploid	autopolyploid	$2n=4x=32$	PN	SRR2040812
	<i>A. cebennensis</i>	WGS	diploid		$2n=2x=16$	PN	SRR2040777
	<i>A. croatica</i>	WGS	diploid		$2n=2x=16$	PN	SRR2040778
	<i>A. halleri ssp. ovirensis</i>	WGS	diploid		$2n=2x=16$	PN	SRR2040785
	<i>A. kamchatica subsp. kamchatica</i>	WGS	tetraploid	allopolyploid	$2n=4x=32$	PN	DRR054581
	<i>A. lyrata ssp. petraea</i>	WGS	diploid		$2n=2x=16$	PN	SRR2040797
	<i>A. lyrata ssp. petraea</i>	WGS	tetraploid	autopolyploid	$2n=4x=32$	PN	SRR2040828
	<i>A. pedemontana</i>	WGS	diploid		$2n=2x=16$	PN	SRR2040802
	<i>A. suecica</i>	WGS	tetraploid	allopolyploid	$2n=4x=26$	PN	SRR2084157
<i>A. thaliana</i>	WGS	diploid		$2n=2x=10$	1KG	SRR1945833	
<i>Capsella</i> (outgroup)	<i>C. rubella</i>	WGS				PN	SRR2082718

^a PN = Novikova et al. (2016); 1KG = Cao et al. (2011)

194 Table S2 | **Number of polymorphisms and read depth for *Brassicaceae* samples, based on**
 195 ***A. lyrata* reference genome.** Number of SNPs, number of indels, and average read depth for
 196 each of the accessions included in the analysis. Read depth was computed by including all sites
 197 (variant, non-variant, and missing sites) within the set of target genes included in the analysis.

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199	Species	# SNPs	# indels	Average read depth
200	<i>A. arenosa ssp. arenosa (2X)</i>	1,927,290	486,944	20
	<i>A. arenosa ssp. arenosa (4X, auto)</i>	1,880,266	463,420	37
201	<i>A. cebennensis</i>	1,325,615	337,940	14
	<i>A. croatica</i>	1,612,635	396,621	27
202	<i>A. halleri ssp. ovirensis</i>	1,422,133	361,123	22
	<i>A. kamchatica subsp. kamchatica (4X, allo)</i>	1,297,177	270,323	135
203	<i>A. lyrata ssp. petraea (2X)</i>	807,707	202,832	50
	<i>A. lyrata ssp. petraea (4X, auto)</i>	1,431,075	332,621	75
204	<i>A. pedemontana</i>	1,428,619	361,850	20
	<i>A. suecica (4X, allo)</i>	1,818,559	347,705	169
205	<i>A. thaliana</i>	2,022,218	526,730	53
206	<i>C. rubella</i>	2,108,561	536,814	19

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219 Figure S1 | **Unimodal convergence** - (a) nested ancestral species. (b) ancestral species are sister
 220 species. The allopolyploid's parental species were removed from the phylogeny prior to running
 221 the analysis.

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240 Figure S2 | **Phylogenetic origins of *A. kamchatica* confirmed using polarized intronic**
241 **sequences** – Species tree cladograms for the *Brassicaceae* genus, including the allotetraploid *A.*
242 *kamchatica*, obtained with ASTRAL based on 639 (N=1) to 565 (N=2) gene families (intronic
243 sequences only). *A. halleri* and *A. lyrata* were identified in previous studies as the parental
244 species (●) of *A. kamchatica*. **(a)** Species tree obtained after the first iteration (N=1). *A.*
245 *kamchatica* sequence polarized (●) using *A. lyrata* as the reference sequence (●). *A. kamchatica*
246 pairs with *A. halleri*. **(b)** Species tree obtained after the second iteration (N=2). *A. halleri*, having
247 been identified as a parental species during the previous iteration, is now the polarizing reference
248 sequence. *A. kamchatica* pairs with *A. lyrata*. Pie charts show the quartet support for each branch.
249 Precise support values are shown for the focal clade containing the allotetraploid species. Only
250 the *A. kamchatica* sequence is polarized. Species containing diploid (2X) and autotetraploid (4X,
251 auto) variants are labeled individually. Species with no label are diploid. **Barplots** on the right-
252 hand side show frequency with which *A. kamchatica* pairs with other species and is based on
253 phylogenetic analysis of individual gene families using IQ-TREE2. Blocks in gray indicate
254 groupings with more than one species (shown only if support $\geq 4\%$, for clarity purposes).
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273 Figure S3 | **Phylogenetic origins of *A. suecica* confirmed using polarized intronic sequences**
274 – Species tree cladograms for the Brassicaceae genus, including the allotetraploid *A. suecica*,
275 obtained with ASTRAL based on 554 (N=1) to 1057 (N=2) gene families (intronic sequences
276 only). *A. thaliana* and *A. arenosa* were identified in previous studies as the parental species (●)
277 of *A. suecica*. **(a)** Species tree obtained after the first iteration (N=1). *A. suecica* sequence
278 polarized (●) using *A. thaliana* as the reference sequence (●). *A. suecica* pairs with *A. arenosa*.
279 **(b)** Species tree obtained after the second iteration (N=2). *A. arenosa*, having been identified as
280 a parental species during the previous iteration, is now the polarizing reference sequence. *A.*
281 *suecica* pairs with *A. thaliana*. Pie charts show the quartet support for each branch. Precise
282 support values are shown for the focal clade containing the allotetraploid species. Only the *A.*
283 *suecica* sequence is polarized. Species containing diploid (2X) and autotetraploid (4X, auto)
284 variants are labeled individually. Species with no label are diploid. **Barplots** on the right-hand
285 side show frequency with which *A. suecica* pairs with other species and is based on phylogenetic
286 analysis of individual gene families using IQ-TREE2. Blocks in gray indicate groupings with
287 more than one species (shown only if support $\geq 4\%$, for clarity purposes).
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306 Figure S4 | **Phylogenetic origins of *A. kamchatica* confirmed using polarized exonic**
307 **sequences, with mapping and variant calling based on *A. halleri* reference genome** – Species
308 tree cladograms for the *Brassicaceae* genus, including the allotetraploid *A. kamchatica*, obtained
309 with ASTRAL based on 865 (N=1) to 864 (N=2) gene families (exonic sequences only). *A.*
310 *halleri* and *A. lyrata* were identified in previous studies as the parental species (●) of *A.*
311 *kamchatica*. (a) Species tree obtained after the first iteration (N=1). *A. kamchatica* sequence
312 polarized (●) using *A. lyrata* as the reference sequence (●). *A. kamchatica* pairs with *A. halleri*.
313 (b) Species tree obtained after the second iteration (N=2). *A. halleri*, having been identified as a
314 parental species during the previous iteration, is now the polarizing reference sequence. *A.*
315 *kamchatica* pairs with *A. lyrata*. Pie charts show the quartet support for each branch. Precise
316 support values are shown for the focal clade containing the allotetraploid species. Only the *A.*
317 *kamchatica* sequence is polarized. Species containing diploid (2X) and autotetraploid (4X, auto)
318 variants are labeled individually. Species with no label are diploid. Barplots on the right-hand
319 side show frequency with which *A. kamchatica* pairs with other species and is based on
320 phylogenetic analysis of individual gene families using IQ-TREE2. Blocks in gray indicate
321 groupings with more than one species (shown only if support $\geq 4\%$, for clarity purposes).

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344 **Figure S5 | Phylogenetic origins of *A. suecica* confirmed using polarized exonic sequences,**
345 **with mapping and variant calling based on *A. halleri* reference genome** – Species tree
346 cladograms for the Brassicaceae genus, including the allotetraploid *A. suecica*, obtained with
347 ASTRAL based on 750 (N=1) to 2421 (N=2) gene families (exonic sequences only). *A. thaliana*
348 and *A. arenosa* were identified in previous studies as the parental species (●) of *A. suecica*. (a)
349 Species tree obtained after the first iteration (N=1). *A. suecica* sequence polarized (●) using *A.*
350 *thaliana* as the reference sequence (●). *A. suecica* pairs with *A. arenosa*. (b) Species tree obtained
351 after the second iteration (N=2). *A. arenosa*, having been identified as a parental species during
352 the previous iteration, is now the polarizing reference sequence. *A. suecica* pairs with *A. thaliana*.
353 Pie charts show the quartet support for each branch. Precise support values are shown for the
354 focal clade containing the allotetraploid species. Only the *A. suecica* sequence is polarized.
355 Species containing diploid (2X) and autotetraploid (4X, auto) variants are labeled individually.
356 Species with no label are diploid. Barplots on the right-hand side show frequency with which *A.*
357 *suecica* pairs with other species and is based on phylogenetic analysis of individual gene families
358 using IQ-TREE2. Blocks in gray indicate groupings with more than one species (shown only if
359 support $\geq 4\%$, for clarity purposes).

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